

Microbial Degradation of Acetothioacetanilide and Its Chelates

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The microbial degradation of acetothioacetanilide and its twelve chelates with metal ions like Ag(I), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Pt(II), Pd(II), Cu(II), Fe(III), Au(III) and Se(IV) by six wild strain bacteria, *Bacillus* Sp., *Rhizobium* Sp., *E. coli*, *Pseudomonas* Sp., *Staphylococcus* Sp., and *Streptococcus* Sp. have been studied in the presence as also in the absence of medium containing K_2HPO_4 and $MgSO_4$. No nitrogen-carbon-containing substrate was added. The following general sequence in the growth rate was observed: *Pseudomonas* Sp. > *Staphylococcus* Sp. > *Streptococcus* Sp. > *Bacillus* Sp. > *E. coli* > *Rhizobium* Sp.

MICROBIAL degradation of several organic chelants and their metallic chelates have been reported.

Tiedje and Manson¹ studied the microbial degradation of nitrilotriacetate in soils while Tiedje² reported similar studies with ethylenediamine tetraacetate. Firestone and Tiedje³ reported the biodegradation of metal-nitrilotriacetate complexes by a *Pseudomonas* species and its mechanism.

Acetothioacetanilide (HATA), $CH_3.CO.CH_2.CS.NHC_6H_5$ is a synthetic ligand containing C, H, N, O and S and form chelates of the first order with various metal ions, which are in general insoluble in water. This reagent, a monothioderivative of acetoacetanilide, $CH_3.CO.CH_2.CONHC_6H_5$ as also the chelates of acetothioacetanilide have been found to undergo microbial degradation while the parent molecule without sulphur does not do so. The studies were carried out with twelve metal-chelates and six wild strain bacteria. Another interesting feature observed was that the presence of the chelates in the liquid culture medium supports the growth of several bacteria without any substrate containing nitrogen or carbon.

Bunch and Ettinger⁴ studied the biodegradation of some potential organic substitutes for phosphate. The chelates of acetothioacetanilide were also found to undergo such degradation in the absence of phosphate.

Experimental

Preparation of Acetothioacetanilide: The ligand was prepared in the laboratory following the methods due to Barnikow⁵ and his coworkers.

Preparation of the Chelates of Acetothioacetanilide^{6,7}:

The following chelates $Zn(ATA)_2$, $Cd(ATA)_2$, $Hg(ATA)_2$, $Se(ATA)_2$, $Ni(ATA)_2$, $Co(ATA)_2$, $Pt(ATA)_2$, $Pd(ATA)_2$, $Fe(ATA)_3$, $Cu(ATA)_2$, $Ag(ATA)$ and $Au(ATA)_3$ were prepared by the addition of an ethanolic solution of acetothioacetanilide to a hot acidified solution containing the metal ion and then adjusting the pH with aqueous ammonia. The pH ranges are given below:

Chelates	pH	Chelates	pH
$Zn(ATA)_2$	7.0-7.5	$Pt(ATA)_2$	2.5-5.0
$Cd(ATA)_2$	6.9-8.7	$Pd(ATA)_2$	2.7-4.1
$Eg(ATA)_2$	1.3-1.8	$Fe(ATA)_3$	7.1-8.3
$Se(ATA)_2$	0.28-0.68	$Cu(ATA)_2$	7.7-9.0
$Ni(ATA)_2$	6.4-6.9	$Ag(ATA)$	6.1-7.0
$Co(ATA)_2$	6.7-12.0	$Au(ATA)_3$	4.3-5.6

Bacteria taken:

The bacteria studied are *Bacillus* Sp., *Rhizobium* Sp., *E. coli*, *Pseudomonas* Sp., *Staphylococcus* Sp. and *Streptococcus* Sp. These inocula were taken in sterilised culture tubes following the normal transfer technique using a micro pipette.

Preparation of medium: Prepared by dissolving 0.5 g of dipotassium hydrogen phosphate and 0.2 g of magnesium sulphate heptahydrate in 1 litre of water.

Procedure: An alcoholic solution of the chelate was taken in a sterilised culture tube inside the culture-room. The solvent was evaporated by exposure to infrared radiation in the same room to avoid contamination. To each tube 5 ml of sterilised water, 5 ml of medium and the specific inoculum were added. The strains were allowed to grow at a temperature of 33° in the presence of sunlight. With the elapse of time, the growth of the bacteria with time was followed microscopically.

TABLE 1—GROWTH STUDY IN PRESENCE OF LIGHT AND AIR TIME : 36 hrs, pH : 7, TEMPERATURE : 33°C
LIQUID MEDIUM (a) CONTAINING, (b) WITHOUT K₂HPO₄ AND MgSO₄.

HATA-Complex of	<i>Bacillus</i> Sp.		<i>Rhizobium</i> Sp.		<i>E. coli</i>		<i>Streptococcus</i> Sp.		<i>Staphylococcus</i> Sp.		<i>Pseudomonas</i> Sp.	
	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)
Zinc	++	+	++	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-
Cadmium	++	+	++	+	+	+	+	+	++	+	+	+
Mercury	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Selenium	++	-	-	-	++	-	++	-	++	-	+	-
Nickel	-	-	++	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	++	+
Cobalt	+	+	++	+	++	+	+	+	+	+	++	+
Platinum	-	-	++	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+
Palladium	++	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	++	+	+	+
Iron	++	-	-	-	++	-	++	-	++	-	+	-
Copper	-	-	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
Silver	-	-	-	(slight)	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Gold	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
HATA	+	-	-	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	+

++ rapid growth, + growth (slow), - no growth.

For each strain and each complex three different cultures were studied. In another series of experiments similar procedure was followed excepting the addition of the medium, i.e., in the absence of phosphate and magnesium. All these results are given in Table 1.

The growth rates were recorded by comparison to blank solutions, i.e., solutions without the bacterial strains.

Discussion

The growth study in the medium containing beef-extract, yeast-extract, dipotassium hydrogen phosphate and magnesium sulphate did not indicate much alteration in the liquid culture medium. Only the growth of *E. coli* in palladium complex was noticed. It was interesting to observe that the ligand containing no sulphur atom, i.e., acetoacetanilide did not support the growth of these wild strain bacteria. But the sulphur containing derivative of the ligand supported the growth of the above said strains. In the acetothioacetanilide the following sequence in the growth rate was observed :

Pseudomonas Sp. > *Staphylococcus* Sp. > *Streptococcus* Sp. > *Bacillus* Sp. > *E. coli* > *Rhizobium* Sp.

In all cases the growth either in the chelates or in the monothioligand gave the same water insoluble precipitate. The product so formed due to the bacterial growth was voluminous in nature and water insoluble. The absorbance curves of the solutions of those products in chloroform were similar in nature in all cases and independent of the chelates. The curve gave no maxima in the range 350 nm to 1000 nm, where all the chelates and

the ligand were known to exhibit their λ_{max} . This showed that the degradation product was different from the unreacted chelates. The aqueous layer contained the free metal ion and no metal was detected in the insoluble portion. This indicated the degradation of the chelates by bacteria.

After several days when the metal ion concentration exceeded the lethal dose for the specific bacteria all the strains become dead. Otherwise in all cases the daughter species of the bacterial strains were small and in the aggregated position. This aggregation was possibly due to the nonseparation of the cells.

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